

EDITORIAL POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING THE INFORMATION CULTURE OF 10-11 CLASS STUDENTS IN THE INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Komilova Ziroatkhan Murodjon kizi

Researcher of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

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***Abstract.** There are considered in the article the issues of creation among the pedagogic team the innovation environment, development of scientific-methodological training of teachers, directing their professional activity to innovative pedagogical process. Special attention is paid to the issues of methodic activity improvement in public schools, creation of pedagogical innovations, learning, synthesis and implementation.*

***Keyword:** education, breeding, innovation, science, technical, information-communicational technologies, quality and efficiency, standards, pedagogic process, modernization of education, innovation, innovation activity, process of innovation, optimization, high resulting, public schools.*

The process of developing the information culture of 10-11th grade students in the innovative educational process is based on the following principles: upbringing and education according to nature; editorial management of this process; the principle of culturally appropriate upbringing and education; the principle of variability and the beginning of creativity; integration (unification); principles of dialogization and repersonalization. We clarify our understanding of these principles.

The principle of dialogization and repersonalization (personalization) of interaction between editors and students implies building the process of life activity in the school Internet circle on the basis of such forms of interaction, which are built taking into account the age and capabilities of students of upper classes. . Cooperation, requiring dialogue between editors and students, should be the basis of mutual activity. In this case, even if the dialogue is conducted with a group, the dialogue is directed to each participant.

Concluding the description of the above principles, it should be emphasized that they are the main requirements for the process we organize, the main rules of activity.

Following the logic of the dissertation, the process of forming the information culture of students is designed based on the implementation of a systematic, activity-based, technological and integrative approach.

We used the systematic approach to build the theory of the research medium, to synthesize various knowledge about the medium (science), to determine the content of information culture formation and to justify the editorial conditions of its modeling. The principle of the systematic approach is to understand the integrity of the event (phenomenon) of information culture and to overcome the isolation of a single methodological base in the study of traditional components such as information technology, network (virtual) communication culture, computer skills (literacy), "information implementation of the content of the concept of "culture" in accordance with the thesis (main idea) that "the whole is greater than the sum of its components" as a guarantee of effective activity in solving the problem of the level of education

of high school students in the field of information allows to ensure understanding at the expense of. The essence of the system approach is reflected in the following rules that help to determine the characteristics of system objects and improve them

a) the integrity of the system in relation to the external environment, the study of the system together with the environment. From the point of view of this rule, educational issues are independent issues, but they are studied in close connection with social and economic development and the demands of society;

b) dividing the whole into components leading to the separation of elements. The properties of the elements depend on their belonging to a certain system, and the properties of the system are not determined (determined) by the properties of its elements or their sum;

c) all the elements of the system are in complex relations and interactivity, among them it is called the relationship that forms the system, and it is necessary to distinguish the most important (that is, the element) that defines this system. In the "Open" educational system, the relationship between the person and various conditions and sources of education, and in the "cracked" educational system - the "educator-pedagogy" relationship is considered as this connection;

g) the set of elements means the structure (structure) and organization of system objects. These concepts represent a certain arrangement of the system, the interrelationship and interdependence of its elements. For example, a system of categories that reflects the main elements of any goal-oriented, including editorial system, is as follows: goals-content-conditions-means-implementation and ways of development-results;

d) a special method of regulating relations between system elements is management, which includes setting goals, choosing tools, monitoring results, and reforming (correcting).

The activity-based approach was used to ensure the implementation of the editorial model, to form the skills and education of the student, and to implement the continuous and continuous process of forming the information culture of students in the Internet club at the school. The principle of the activity-based approach is not from the point of view of the librarian who tries to understand how a library, information service or computer is structured, and to acquaint him with the finer points (details) of information and computer technology, but from the perspective of such persons. It means that it should be constructed from the point of view of consumption and use, arising from the information tasks that need to be solved during professional (rroprofessional) or leisure activities [2].

The essence of the activity-based approach is to study the real process of interaction of a person with the environment, which ensures the solution of certain important tasks of life. In this case, a person performs a sequence of various actions and acts as a subject of cross-activity, an active beginning (the beginning of activity).

From the point of view of application to the problem of formation of information culture, the activity-based approach means to identify and describe (depict) the methods of action in the activity that should lead to the increase of the nature and structure of this culture and the full acquisition of relevant knowledge by students. . At the same time, the acquisition of knowledge leads to the strengthening of certain actions, the formation of general abilities and methods of behavior of students, and the acquisition of new actions. Knowledge is not simply transmitted, students acquire (possess) it in the course of their activities. In the process of carrying out such activities, the skills related to the meaningful analysis and design of the products of the activity

are of great importance.

The principle of the technological approach allows a person to consider the set of methods and tools for the formation of information culture as a redagogical technology. This principle requires the detailed determination of the final result and its accuracy as a basis for obtaining products with specified parameters.

The process of forming a person's information culture is only if an activity program with a clearly defined goal, a defined sequence of actions leading to the achievement of the goal (curriculum) is defined; if there are means to implement the set goal (educational-methodical, technical, etc.); if each step has defined requirements for the final product (knowledge and skills); It has the status of technology only if there are tools (tests, questionnaires, etc.) that measure the level of information culture [2].

For the success of the process of student socialization, we used the complex (all-in-one) approach. This includes: influence on different (cognitive-worldview, emotional-volitional, positive-result-practical) spheres of the person; all areas of a person's life (family, class, educational institution, etc.); approaches to the use of various methods and tools of education and upbringing.

Based on the above principles and approaches to the formation of the information culture of high school students in the Internet club as a group educational organization at the school, we determined the editorial conditions that ensure the effectiveness of its use.

Therefore, redagogical conditions are a situation specially created by redagogues for the purpose of systematic support for self-development and (or) professional improvement of a person's abilities within the framework of his own circumstances and in accordance with the social ideal.

The analysis of the current practice of using new information technologies in general education schools shows that the formation of information culture, which is carried out within the informatics school course, is not of a clear systematic nature, but the complexity of the construction of subject-subject relations in the mutual activities of teachers and students is a high class. It has been shown that influencing the independent choice of activity directions does not allow him to take the active point of view (position) he wants, which in turn is reflected in the formation of the information culture of high school students. This served to distinguish the design of the club activity program taking into account the age characteristics and interests of the students of upper classes as a prerequisite.

The program was created taking into account the following age characteristics of high school students:

- it is possible to understand (understand) the offered educational information (information) independently, and students can choose the forms of receiving information (retrieving);

- rolilog - "the ability to think about a problem in the presence of blind points of view, which, in turn, in its development must pass to the mode of constructive monologue (the ability to discuss the problem with oneself in the mode of dialogue and rolilog)";

- a high level of complexity, which ensures the freedom of choice and the need to define one's own point of view on the visibility of the issues under consideration;

- the diversity of educational content: analytical-logical, figurative, practical, algorithmic, due to the presentation of the way of introducing this educational material to children with

different learning styles;

- presentation of ways to solve the problems of personal and professional self-determination in the content;
- increase a certain system of values that allows to define (identify) one's own system in the content;
- "transtextuality" that ensures a high level of independence in mastering the content.

This educational program includes those interrelated blocks that lead to the effectiveness of the process of formation of information culture - as a result of its implementation, a certain level of mastering of knowledge in the field of information technologies, information society the cognitive block, which involves the development of the information style of thinking that corresponds to the requirements of (adequate); emotional-value block, this block is aimed at forming the moral direction of high school students, helping them determine their socially significant future; Oratory-activity block that allows you to strengthen the acquired knowledge, skills and emotional experiences in practice. In order to implement this program in the Internet circle, classes are held on programming, computer graphics, web design, working on the Internet, and working with electronic networks.

In addition, the activity program of the Internet club at the school allows high school students to implement their projects in practice, to discuss current issues related to information technologies and the problems of modern information society, and to organize an independent learning experience. , includes interpersonal, spiritual-practical, game activities in the process of communication.

The block-module principle of building the educational program made it possible to distinguish both the "core" part of the "Basics of Information Culture" course and its variable, changing part. The permanent, invariant (unchanging) part of the course is aimed at solving the following tasks: explaining the introduction of the information invasion of the development of world civilization (civilization), forming an understanding of the complexity and variety of information resources available in society; arming them with algorithms for search and analytical-synthetic processing, extracting and evaluating information, changing compressed information and obtaining new information on this basis; to teach them rational ways and methods of preparing and processing the results of their independent educational, research and professional activities in the conditions of large-scale introduction of new information technologies. The part of the "Fundamentals of Information Culture" course, which varies depending on the category of students, takes into account age, the nature of the activity, the profile (direction) and level of education, interest, the level of information culture, the need for information and other factors.

Studying the Internet club at the school as an educational organization, we came to the conclusion that its activity is, on the one hand, passionate and externally oriented, and on the other hand, it should be necessary (necessary, required) for the school community. . This can be done when students of higher grades join the information supply of the school community.

The concept of "school community" appeared in edagogy and psychology several decades ago. In Europe and America, this approach to school reform has become widespread, and it still occupies one of the leading positions today. It is based on the principles of democracy, collegiality (co-operative governance), school effectiveness, situational leadership, student-teacher interaction, and focuses on both outcomes and the learning process (i.e., learning).

students' learning) and also applied to teaching (i.e., the activity of the student) [3].

The concept of interaction is interpreted differently in different disciplines. In the dictionary of philosophy, interaction is defined as "a general form of communication and events that take place in mutual exchange." In editorial literature, the concept of "cross-activity" is defined as a general form of development that mutually transforms objects and events in two ways (mutually) and brings each of them to a new state.

Interactivity in philosophy is understood as a complex, diverse process in which the change of subjects occurs not only in relation to each other, but also as a result of each other. The essence of interaction is the continuity of direct and reverse effects, the combination of changes of subjects that affect each other. In addition, cross-activity is a holistic (integral), functionally differentiated (differentiated), self-developing system.

Philosophers indicate the following signs of interaction as a social phenomenon: simultaneous existence of objects; duality of relations, subject and object to subject interaction; legality of communications at the level of substance; that the changes in the parties cause each other (cause each other); the activity of objects [4].

The substantive basis of interaction is the intellectual, expressive-expressive, instrumental, social values recognized as such by the society and (or) the organization. Values can be given and expressed in the form of norms and rules of the life of the educational organization developed on the basis of the effectiveness of social activities. Among them, the dialogic aspect of viewing another (a person, a group, the author of a cultural object) as a subject of social life, as a carrier of one's own interests and needs occupies a central place. A direct and specific indication of effectiveness is the development (development) of the main features of the interaction of the participants of this process, which are implemented in the form of norms and rules of the editorial process:

- mutual knowledge - the objectivity of knowing each other's personal characteristics, best aspects, interests, and interests by studying each other;
- seeking to get to know each other better, mutual interest in each other;
- to understand the common purpose, generality and unity of tasks of the mutual activity faced by editors and schoolchildren through mutual (each other) understanding;
- accepting each other's difficulties, worries, and concerns;
- understanding behavioral incentives - motives in different situations;
- relevance-adequacy of assessment and self-assessment;
- compliance with predetermined goals and tasks (rules of conduct) for cooperative activities;
- in mutual relations - politeness, paying attention to each other's opinions and suggestions;
- emotional readiness for joint activity, satisfaction with its results;
- respect, care, concern for each other's point of view (consent); seeking formal and informal communication;
- the creative nature of relationships that encourage children's initiative and independence;
- through mutual actions - implementation of constant communication (dialogue), active participation in joint activities;
- initiative in establishing various relations provided by both sides;
- demonstration of the effectiveness of working together (quantity, quality, speed of

work), mutual assistance, coordination of actions based on agreement;

- readiness to use each other in different situations, to help, to support each other;
- the ability to agree and reach agreement on controversial issues;
- taking each other's opinions into account when organizing work;

- based on the form and reasonable, the effectiveness of the correct mutual feedback, changing the behavior and behavior methods after giving recommendations to each other;

- taking each other as an example to imitate.

In general, the development of mutual activity between the participants of the educational process can be assessed by enriching the content of their joint activities and communication, methods and forms of mutual activity, expanding external and business relations, and realizing coherence. The results of our research made it possible to conclude that the development of information culture of 10-11 graders in the Internet circle will be effective in the implementation of the following editorial conditions:

-designing the activity program of the club based on the age characteristics and interests of the high school students;

-inclusion of high school students in the information supply of the life of the school community;

-to complement the activity of circle life with effective norms and rules of social interaction.

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